

D6.1 Project Logo and Website

for

HORIZON-EIC-2023-TRANSITION-01

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

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FASS

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1 Executive summary

Within the scope of this deliverable, a logo, a website and a LinkedIn account for the FASS project were created. All elements follow a common style guide and act as the project's public window to inform stakeholders about project developments and to attract potential customers and collaborators. The website includes a section for sharing information about the project and the consortium, a newsfeed to communicate and disseminate results and a contact form to encourage stakeholders to engage with the consortium. The LinkedIn account supports the website by further spreading news of the FASS consortium and by linking to the page whenever possible to boost its visibility among a wider audience.

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2 Detailed report on the deliverable

2.1 Background

The FASS website and logo act as public window with unified branding and will increase the visibility of the project. The website will provide information to potential customers, early adopters, collaborators, investors and other stakeholders about the project and the consortium behind it. Complementary to social media, personal interaction and other communication channels, it will be the central point for project dissemination and communication and serves as a first point of contact for interest groups to establish direct interactions with the project and its partners. The website and logo were created in July 2024, and the website content will be extended and altered over the course of the project based on new achievements, insights or feedback from stakeholders.

2.2 Logo and style

The logo was designed in a common effort by all consortium members during the FASS kick-off meeting in Basel in July 2024. A solid green design (#69CF90) was chosen to underline the sustainable nature of the project and the FASS technology (Figure 1). Dark blue (#012147) was chosen as secondary colour and alternative background of the logo. The logo with this background colour will be used for LinkedIn. This colour will also be used as the background colour of the website. A third colour, light blue (#6CE6E9), was chosen as an accent colour for highlighted design elements. The rest of the website is kept in white, including the menu links. Reports, presentations and other material related to the project will follow the above-mentioned colour scheme.

Fast and Accurate Solubility for Sustainability

*Fast and Accurate Solubility
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Figure 1: Versions of the FASS logo with white and blue background

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2.3 Website structure and content

In an initial attempt to provide early information to the public, a preliminary landing page was launched and highlighted in the FASS kick-off press release from 22.07.2024 (Figure 2). Initially, the site displayed a brief description of the project; the consortium members, including links to their home pages; and the contact details of the main communication contacts.

Figure 2: Initial FASS landing page for early information and press release.

In a second step, the initial landing page was replaced with a full homepage (<https://www.fass-solubility.eu/>) making use of the RI-VIS toolkit (<https://toolkit.rivis.eu/home>). The new landing introduces the merits of the technology and includes a newsfeed and contacts to get in touch with the consortium for collaboration (Figure 3). The top menu guides visitors to the sites “The Project” and “The Team”, where the FASS technology, the project work packages and the roles of each partner are comprehensively explained. Links to the partner institutions are provided. The menu also contains a dynamic “News” section to disseminate and communicate material and other important milestones and outcomes of the project. The first news item, the FASS press release, has already been published at the time of this deliverable report. Throughout the development of the website, contact to potential customers, early adopters and new collaborators was identified as priority. A contact form was installed to encourage stakeholders to reach out and provide feedback, suggest a collaboration or, more specifically, request an instrument demonstration or compound solubility measurement. Such stakeholder contact could lead to the first case studies and testimonials from customers outside the consortium and new applications of the instrumentation even beyond the project goals.

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Figure 3: Full FASS homepage with subsites “The Project”, “The Team”, “News” and contact form.

The FASS project communication will be supported by the FASS LinkedIn page (https://www.linkedin.com/company/fass-%E2%80%93-fast-and-accurate-solubility-for-sustainability?trk=public_post_reshare_feed-actor-name), which directly links to the website and where FASS communications are centrally distributed (Figure 4). To reach a wider community, posts will be further shared with a wider community including potential collaborators and customers through the partner profiles, which have approximately 80,000 followers in sum. The LinkedIn account will be also linked on the website.

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Info

FASS is a project funded by the European Commission, and by the State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) in Switzerland.

Solubility measurement is a standard test that is required for every chemical that is produced or tested. However, measuring solubility is a time/labour-intensive process that requires substantial quantities of chemicals. State-of-the-Art solubility measurements are either fast but inaccurate or slow but accurate and require excess of chemicals. FASS is based on high-efficiency second harmonic scattering that combines the analytical advantages of current solubility measurements, fast and accurate, while achieving cutting edge performance in sensitivity and reliability.

Figure 4: FASS LinkedIn channel.

3 Conclusions and next steps

With the beginning of the FASS project, a logo with a colour scheme, a website for stakeholder information and customer contact and a LinkedIn account were established to enhance the visibility of the consortium and its mission. During the lifetime of the project, the website will further evolve to share additional information about the project. While general information about the project will remain rather static, the news section will be updated regularly to share important results of the projects.

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